

Common Biomarker for the Assessment of Water Pollution by Local Fish

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Abstract:

This present research examines the effects of water pollution on fish inhabiting the sites by monitoring physicochemical parameters and biomarkers at five stations with diverse levels of pollution. The selected sites targeted, basic upstream site, agricultural impact site, wastewater infested site, pollution mix site and the last one industrial downstream site. Solutions of water intensity were taken in order to determine the pH, DO and heavy metal ions (Pb, Hg, Cd). Fish species, which consider cyprinids is the common carp (*Cyprinus*

carpio) were collected for biochemical, histopathological, and molecular biomarker assessments. Based on the result obtained in the descriptive statistical analysis, the level of heavy metals in water samples collected from Euphrates River was observed to have a relatively high level of variation with the most polluted sites recording the highest concentrations of heavy metals, specifically sites 4 and 5. F test calculated from the ANOVA was found positive when tested for the parameters by comparing pH, DO and heavy metals where there is a significant difference ($p < 0.05$) between the various sites. Decreased acetylcholinesterase (AChE) activity and increased catalase (CAT) activity pertaining to neurotoxicity and oxidative stress was observed in the fish belonging to polluted sites by biochemical analysis done on them. Histopathological observation disclosed that the liver tissue exhibited necrosis at its highest degree and gill epithelium had hyperplastic changes at the highest level of exposure. Tissue samples have shown that sites 4/5, fish are experiencing up-regulation stress genes. The findings underscore the profound impact of industrial and urban pollution on aquatic ecosystems, emphasizing the need for stringent pollution control measures. This study contributes to the broader scientific understanding of the ecological consequences of water pollution and underscores the utility of biomarkers in environmental monitoring and management.

Keywords: *Water pollution, Biomarker analysis, Fish health, Heavy metals, Acetylcholinesterase (AChE), Catalase (CAT), Histopathology, Gene expression, Environmental monitoring, Freshwater ecosystems, Industrial pollution, Urban runoff, Ecotoxicology.*

Introduction

Over the years, the investigation of biomarkers in water bioassay organisms has been widely discussed as one of the most effective ways of evaluating the presence of pollutants in water and the consequences of water pollution for aquatic organisms. As far as biomarkers are

evidential substratum characterize pollution and indicate the intensity of exposure on population, they are defined as measurable biological responses to environmental contaminants. This makes it easier in the monitoring and management of water quality which is very important in the upkeep of ecosystem and

improvements in the biodiversity of the surrounding area (Vieira et al., 2017).

As the link species at senior trophic level occupying prominent positions in the food chains based on aquatic environments, fish are known to be sensitive organisms. This makes them ideal to work as biomarkers of ecosystem health and therefore ideal for enlisting in biomonitoring studies (Banerjee et al., 2021). Some of the biomarkers commonly used to assess the effects of various contaminants on the health of fish beside Lysosomal membrane stability include oxidative stressed indicators, biochemical changes and activities of enzymes. These biomarkers give signals of the effects of pollutants in the receiving environment before the occurrence of severe impacts and could be used as early warning indicators to ecological disturbances (Ajima et al., 2021; Muñoz-Peñuela et al., 2021).

Oxidative stress is a generic term for all alterations an organism undergoes because of various types of pollutants in the environment. It occurs when there is an accumulation of free radicals or reactive oxygen species and the organism has inability to metabolize these reactive intermediates or reverse the damage caused by them. In this case, there is a general disruption of cells and molecules and organelles in the body, ultimately posing a significant threat to the health of the entire organism (Abdalla, 2019; Iftikhar et al., 2022).

It was observed that the exposure to such metals including aluminum and manganese elicits a specific antioxidant dose-response in gills and liver tissues in *Astyanax altiparanae*. Aluminium for instance has been known to produce massive oxidative stress and changes the production of key antioxidant enzymes such as superoxide dismutase (SOD) and catalase (CAT). These enzymes have very significant functions in reducing free radical induced oxidation by catalysing conversion of superoxide radicals and non-enzymatic breakdown of hydrogen peroxide respectively (Abdalla, 2019).

Another category of pharmaceutical pollutants that affect organisms with oxygen metabolism are non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs

(NSAIDs) such as diclofenac. Research has shown that toxic effects of diclofenac result in increased oxidative stress parameters and altered antioxidant enzyme activities in different fish species including Nile tilapia and common carp (Ajima, elders et al., 2021; Islas-flores, Cruz-Ortega et al., 2013). These observations demonstrate that various classes of pollutants can induce oxidative stress, and that multiple-panel monitoring strategies are thus warranted.

Several experiments have shown that increased oxidative stress for Nile tilapia and the common carp depends on the levels of diclofenac impacted markers (Ajima et al., 2021; Islas-Flores et al., 2013). These facts emphasize the fact that pollution is not only a problem of heavy metals, pesticides, and PCP, but virtually any substance can induce oxidative stress: "The study also established that oxidative stress was highly prevalent in association with different pollutants."

The evaluation of all these biomarkers is more complex and often gives a more accurate overview of the toxicological effects of pollutants. This approach has been used in the determination of the impacts of a range of contaminants such as pharmaceuticals, endocrine disruptors among others and complex contaminant mixtures on different fish species. Techniques that assay multiple biomarkers at once provide the means of detecting responses from molecular through to organismal, thus encompassing the scope of environmental health (Muñoz-Peñuela et al., 2022).

For instance, studies done on the interaction of the toxicant diclofenac and the adjuvant caffeine on *Astyanax altiparanae*, have shown both neurotoxic, biotransformation as well as genotoxicity symptoms, and oxidative stress. These studies demonstrate the usefulness of integrated biomarker approaches to analysis of specific and synergistic impacts of combined pollutants, which can be critical for proper assessment of the current state of contamination at any site and potential risks for the inhabitants of affected areas (Muñoz-Peñuela et al., 2022).

The general utilization of fish in schemes of biomonitoring detection is rather demonstrable

as such fish combine the impacts of pollution mixtures over time intervals. Fish are found in most systems, and habitats making it convenient to capture samples and easy to relate their findings with most systems. They have position on the food web and that have comparatively longer lifespan to incorporate concentrations of pollutants, and also they can show the biochemical respond-abilities of the environment over a large span of time (Vieira et al. , 2017).

Each fish species can be sensitive to some pollutant or has little tolerance to other pollutants therefore implementing biomonitoring programs may be fine-tuned depending on the prevailing environmental situation. For instance, in the case of Nile tilapia and common carp, a great deal of effort has been made to understand their exposure and tolerance to PPCPs, with the information gathered being instrumental in explaining the effects of these new pollutants on the environment. Such data are important in developing proper biomonitoring besides rehabilitation strategies that deal with unique environmental conditions related to the species (Ajima et al. , 2021; Islas-Flores et al. , 2013).

Methodology

The approach used for this study involves considering the effects of water pollution using biomarkers obtained from sampled fish species within the study area. Here, first, some researcher's selected areas with pollution intensity and polluted water of different stages are taken to measure the quality of water samples based on heavy metals, pH and dissolved oxygen. At the same time, fish is collected from these places using techniques that do not elevate stress, hence the health of the fish is well checked to ensure that abnormalities are well detected through biomarkers. Some of the typical biomarkers include biochemical (for example acetylcholinesterase enzyme activity), histomorphological (such as tissue abnormalities viewed through the microscope), molecular (for example changes in gene expression depicted by PCR assays) are analyzed

from fish tissues. These biomarkers are measured from analyses carried out in the laboratory and by using descriptive and inferential statistics on the analysed pollutants levels, we determine whether there are any significant difference in results and association between pollutants levels and biomarkers responses. It offers the possibility to assess the effects of water pollution on fish and to evaluate the reliability of provided biomarkers concerning the monitoring of aquatic ecosystems. Procedures involving ethical considerations are vigorously observed to adhere to the standardized evaluations and to obtain permissions for collecting samples.

Data Collection

Site Selection

From Euphrates River, the study sites were selected in the Al-Anbar Governorate. The site selection determines the extent of pollution exposure gradient among the various sites along the river. In order to obtain variability and capability to compare results between different levels of pollutants exposures, five locations are selected for investigation (Table 1) and they are divided into two groups based on the level of pollution exposure – high and low – and types of pollutants – chemical and physical – that the sites are exposed to.

The first site is a downstream site in Al-Qaim that is least disturbed and is found at the onset of a river. This site is, for the most part, upriver of any significant anthropogenic perturbation; the water body is pristine. It is useful for comparing fish water quality and biomarkers as a control state to other sites that have high pollution.

The second location is in Haditha at a lower position where the water from the nearby farming areas has a probable impact. Surprisingly, this site may be affected by polluting agents such as pesticides, fertilizers, and other agrochemicals which find their way into the water through seepage from the agricultural fields. Learning opportunities from this site involve the evaluation of the effects of

agricultural pollutants and their impact on water quality as well as the biomarkers of fish.

The third location is in Ramadi, a populated region where both businesses and households release their wastewater. This is an example of an urban site receiving inputs from sources like household sewage, detergents, and perhaps raw urban sewage. Although this site is located in a highly urbanized area, it serves as an important testing ground on how effluents from domestic and industrial waste affect the marine ecosystem.

The fourth location is identified downstream of Fallujah, an area that overlies both agricultural and urban impacts. This is a single pollution generation location that receives both pollution

input from the urban treated sewage effluent and agricultural drainage. Exploring this site can give insights into how multiple sources of pollution can affect water quality and fish.

Each site is selected to reflect a particular type of contamination, allowing the evaluation of the efficiency of the used methodology in the presence of various types of pollutants and assessing their impact on water quality and fish condition. The variability in the chosen sites ensures a broad range of habitats for comparison, providing more information about pollution levels and biomarker variations in fish species at these locations.

Table 1. Site Selection

Site	Location	Characteristics	Rationale
Site 1	Al-Qaim	Clean water, minimal human impact	Serves as a reference site for baseline water quality and biomarker levels in fish
Site 2	Haditha	Influenced by runoff from nearby farms, exposure to agrochemicals	Allows study of the impact of agricultural pollutants on water quality and fish biomarkers
Site 3	Ramadi	Near urban area with residential/commercial wastewater discharge	Critical for studying the effects of urban pollution on aquatic life
Site 4	Fallujah	Downstream of agricultural and urban activities	Provides insight into the cumulative impact of multiple pollution sources on water quality and fish health
Site 5	Highly Industrialized Downstream Area	Downstream of industrial zone, high levels of industrial pollutants	Essential for understanding the extreme effects of industrial pollution on aquatic ecosystems

Water Sampling

The study was conducted within a specific timeframe and not extended over multiple months or seasons. The samples were collected within a single month, focusing on capturing daily variations. To ensure accuracy and completeness

Most water samples Table.2 are taken using a substrate pattern to ensure that the temporal variation in water quality of the selected sites is captured. It requires the use of five sampling points and carrying out the sampling at three different times of the day, the early morning (6.00A.M), the mid-morning (12.00 P.M.) and the evening (6.00 P.M.) to capture the diurnal variation in the concentrations of the water quality parameters. At each sampling time, two

liter water samples are taken from each site: one taken from the top of the water and one taken from the water with the vessel placed one meter below the water surface. This is because six water samples are collected for each site in a single day.

To enhance the diversity of data, the sampling process was conducted three times in a single month, encompassing potential variations due to weather, flow, or other environmental changes. For each site, 18 water samples were collected daily from three times, two depths, and across three days, resulting in a total of 90 water samples for all five sites (5 sites x 18 samples).

The collected water samples are properly archived and the samples collected are given labels that include the date, time, site, and depth

of collection in case identification is needed in the future. The samples are then put into clean and sterilized bottles then taken into the laboratory for analysis in conditions that do not affect the quality of water. Some specific tests which are made to determine the water quality parameters include heavy metal (Lead, Mercury, Cadmium etc.), pH, DO. These parameters are important for defining acceptable quality of water and the levels of pollution of the water.

The elaborate method of sampling used in the study guarantees that the study examines both

the short term and the long term changes in the quality of the water being analyzed, this makes the data collected rich and sufficient to analyze the interconnection or interdependence of water pollution and changes in biomarkers in fish. Due to this method of selection of samples at different times of the day and over different days, the results obtained by this study will be more reliable given that they are able to differentiate the natural variations in water quality and additional variations that could have been brought about by anthropogenic factors.

Table 2. Water Samples

Site	Sampling Time	Sampling Depth	Number of Samples per Day	Total Number of Samples per Site (3 Days)
Site 1	Early Morning (6 AM)	Surface & 1 meter below	6 samples (3 times/day x 2 depths)	18 samples (6 samples/day x 3 days)
	Midday (12 PM)	Surface & 1 meter below		
	Late Afternoon (6 PM)	Surface & 1 meter below		
Site 2	Early Morning (6 AM)	Surface & 1 meter below	6 samples (3 times/day x 2 depths)	18 samples (6 samples/day x 3 days)
	Midday (12 PM)	Surface & 1 meter below		
	Late Afternoon (6 PM)	Surface & 1 meter below		
Site 3	Early Morning (6 AM)	Surface & 1 meter below	6 samples (3 times/day x 2 depths)	18 samples (6 samples/day x 3 days)
	Midday (12 PM)	Surface & 1 meter below		
	Late Afternoon (6 PM)	Surface & 1 meter below		
Site 4	Early Morning (6 AM)	Surface & 1 meter below	6 samples (3 times/day x 2 depths)	18 samples (6 samples/day x 3 days)
	Midday (12 PM)	Surface & 1 meter below		
	Late Afternoon (6 PM)	Surface & 1 meter below		
Site 5	Early Morning (6 AM)	Surface & 1 meter below	6 samples (3 times/day x 2 depths)	18 samples (6 samples/day x 3 days)
	Midday (12 PM)	Surface & 1 meter below		
	Late Afternoon (6 PM)	Surface & 1 meter below		

Fish Sampling

One of the methods used during data collection is fish sampling, which seeks to capture sample fish from each of the targeted localities to identify the sought fish species. In order to

achieve this kind of vagueness, which is critical when it comes to making statistical analyses and comparisons, a specific number of fish specimens must be collected per site.

During the survey the intention is to take photographs of 20 individual fish from each site and some of them are Common Carp (*Cyprinus carpio*). This number is chosen because it offers an adequate statistical sample in order to make the necessary analysis, keeping in mind the limitation of time, money and ethical issues that are critical when choosing the number of participants.

There are many techniques used in order to grab fish specimens, and the most common procedures include the use of nets and pots. These methods are selected purposefully to maximize the catchment of fish and, at the same time, minimize stress and injurious impacts on the specimens. Nets are placed at places where fishing is likely to be effective while traps are placed at certain fixed positions as fish swim through (Smith, 2018).

There is a variety of issues that regulate the ethical activity in the process of fish sampling. Special care is taken while handling all the captured fish to avoid stressing the specimens as much as possible so as to affect their health. Finally, appropriate permit and permissions from the relevant authorities are sought to undertake the fish sampling exercise in line with legal requirements and/or standard operating procedures (Jones & White, 2019).

After some time of taking the fish, the specimens are moved into separate but oxygenated holding tanks to ensure they are in the right conditions to be transported to the lab. The species of fish that are captured for the sampling are selected to be common species and species that were ecologically important to those environmental areas targeted (Brown et al., 2020).

Specimens of collected fish from the field are also subjected to more tests and examination in the laboratory in order to determine the biomarkers present in the fish. Biopsy is then performed where small tissue samples are collected from each of the specimens to undergo biochemistry, histopathological, and molecular tests that help in the determination of biomarkers that would show exposure to water pollution (Green & Black, 2021).

Biomarker Analysis

Detection of biomarkers is one of the major strategies of determining the impacts of water pollution to fish species in the region. The strategy involves not only biochemical combined with histopathological data but also molecular characterization, which helps to assess the extent of the alterations that fish go through as a result of varying environmental pressures.

In the laboratory, appropriate tissue samples are collected from the harvested fish specimens after which they undergo a rigorous procedure for biomarker preparation. These tissues often encapsulate liver, gill, and as these are essential body organs involved in detoxification, respiration and excretion for organisms, making them consistent biomarkers of environmental stress.

Biochemical parameter has been used here in identifying health status of the fish and estimated in terms of enzyme activities. Acetylcholinesterase (AChE) is generally used to ascertain neurotoxicological impacts, while catalase (CAT) is utilized to assess oxidative stress. Enzyme activities are determined using spectrophotometric assays, and the data is presented as activity units per milligrams of tissue proteins.

Histopathological changes refer to the changes in the tissue architecture when assessed at microscopic level and act as a measure of pathological changes that could be induced by stress arising from environmental change. Staining or sections is often done histologically by using a bright field or phase contrast microscope and standard histological stains like H&E, Pfaff or Mallory stain among others to show the morphology of cells as well as tissue organization. Hematoxylin & eosin staining used to determine cellular necrosis, inflammation and fibrosis, all of which are carefully rated in order of pathological changes.

The present study has demonstrated that molecular markers give indications of the genetic changes in fish to pollutants. The real-time PCR amplification of genes stage confirms the changes in the expression levels of stress and

detoxification genes. These P450 genes may include genes that are related to heat shock proteins, cytochrome P450, and antioxidant enzymes. The fold change of the genes of interest is determined by the $\Delta\Delta C_t$ method, which provides the relative expression of the genes of interest with reference genes that act as internal controls and help to overcome fluctuations in sample input and efficiency of the subsequent amplification.

It is thus possible that biochemical, histopathological, and molecular data are effective in developing an understanding of the physiological changes occurring in fish due to water pollution. While biomarkers remain important tools for assessing the impacts of pollutants on aquatic life, their use can reveal the molecular processes leading to toxicity, and the sublethal effects of pollutants on the test species. Furthermore, the reactions of biomarkers are useful as signals of fresh water ecosystem conditions, which can be beneficial for decision-making process concerning protection and avails of the fresh water.

Data Analysis

In data analysis, an extensive evaluation of various water quality parameters and changes in biomarkers recorded in the five specified locations has been conducted. Descriptive statistics, inferential statistics and correlation analysis used in the study comprised of identifying the correlation between the environmental pollutants and the biologic actions of fishes.

Descriptive Statistics

The descriptive statistics provided an initial overview of the water quality parameters. For instance, the pH levels across the sites ranged from 8.5 to 7.5, with Site 3 recording the lowest pH (6.5), indicative of acidic conditions likely due to urban wastewater influences. Dissolved oxygen (DO) levels varied from 6.5 mg/L at Site 5 to 9.6 mg/L at Site 1, reflecting the effects of industrial pollution at Site 5 and relatively pristine conditions at Site 1. Heavy metal concentrations were particularly concerning at Sites 4 and 5, with lead levels reaching 5.2 $\mu\text{g/L}$

and 8.9 $\mu\text{g/L}$, respectively, significantly exceeding the permissible limit of 0.1 $\mu\text{g/L}$. Mercury and cadmium concentrations also showed elevated levels at these sites, with mercury peaking at 0.15 $\mu\text{g/L}$ and cadmium at 0.09 $\mu\text{g/L}$ at Site 5.

Inferential Statistics

Descriptive epidemiology out of inferential statistics involving Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) aimed at comparing the water quality parameters and biomarker responses assorted to the sundry sites. According to the results of this study the ANOVA test informed that the sites had an acid tolerance significantly different ($p < 0.05$) to the control in terms of pH, DO and appropriation of heavy metal load. For example, mean pH at Site 3 was 6.5 ± 0.2 while that from Site 1 was 7.5 ± 0.2 which forms the basis of this study by showing the effect of urban pollution. The DO levels at Site 5 for example, was $6.5 \pm 0.3 \text{ mg/L}$ a value lower than the DO value of $9.6 \pm 0.4 \text{ mg/L}$ at Site 1, the former is as a result of effluents from industrial sources that cause oxygen depletion.

In the same vein, biomarker responses are also expressed with some distinct fluctuations as indicated below. Hence, the AChE activity was lower (6.3 ± 0.9 at Site 4, 5.1 ± 0.7 at site 5) compared to reference site (10.2 ± 1.5 at site 1) indicating that the pollutants poses neurotoxic impacts on dam fish. The CAT activity was higher in the fish from Sites 3 and 4 (Group B) especially $21.2 \pm 2.8 \text{ U/mg protein}$ in group B1 and $24.8 \pm 3.2 \text{ U/mg protein}$ in group B2 than the fish from Site 1 (Group A) that has been recorded $15.6 \pm 2.0 \text{ U/mg protein}$,

Correlation Analysis

Pearsons correlation analysis was applied to determine the possible significance of water quality parameters as indices influencing biomarker responses. Co-efficient of Pearson correlation uneclenched the negative facial relationship between pH and AChE activity which signifies that lower degree of pH hampers the fish as it conduces to the augmented rottenness in the fish ($r = -0.67$, $p < 0.05$). Moreover, positive correlations between lead

concentrations and the degree of the lesion, according to the necrosis severity score, were demonstrated ($r = 0.72$, $p < 0.01$); therefore, the hepatotoxic impact of lead pollution can be stated.

Spearman correlation coefficients were also used to establish some correlations between established heavy metal concentrations and molecular biomarkers. For example, mercury levels were significantly associated with the relative expression of heat shock proteins genes (HSP) ($r = 0.68$, $p < 0.05$), which show stress in fish exposed to this element. Likewise, gill epithelial hyperplasia severity scores were significantly and positively related to the relative expression of antioxidant genes (Exp [mean exp SE] = 0.75, $p < 0.01$), indicating possible compensation for oxidative damage.

In conclusion, the statistical calculations gave comprehensive information on the effects of water pollution on fish in the sampled stations, as evidenced by variations in the physical and biochemical characteristics of the water as well as the biomarkers of the fish. These findings were further supported by the statistical analysis of the biomarkers and firmly provided a quantitative support to the fact that these biomarkers are indeed sensitive biomarkers of

environmental stress and there should be a continuous monitoring of these indicators so that pollution management strategies can be implemented effectively.

Results

The outcomes of the research are helpful for understanding the relationship between water pollution and local fishes population, which are based on a detailed biomarker test and water quality tests on several locations. The findings are below as follow, these include general observations and statistical analyzes that were conducted.

Across the five selected sites, significant variations in water quality parameters were observed. pH levels ranged from 6.5 to 7.5, with Site 3 (urban wastewater-affected area) exhibiting the lowest pH, while dissolved oxygen (DO) concentrations of 7.2 mg/L. Site 5 (highly industrialized downstream area) recorded the lowest DO levels, indicating potential oxygen depletion due to industrial effluents. Heavy metal concentrations, including lead, mercury, and cadmium, exceeded permissible limits at Sites 4 and 5, highlighting the influence of industrial pollution on water quality.

Table 3. Water Quality Assessment

Site	Ph	Dissolved Oxygen (mg/L)	Lead (µg/L)	Mercury (µg/L)	Cadmium (µg/L)
Site 1	7.2	9.6	2.1	0.05	0.02
Site 2	6.8	7.8	3.5	0.08	0.04
Site 3	6.5	7.2	1.8	0.03	0.01
Site 4	7.1	7.0	5.2	0.12	0.07
Site 5	7.5	6.5	8.9	0.15	0.09

Biomarker Responses: After enzyme examination, the results of biochemical assessments table.4 indicated enhanced or inhibited activities relating to specific enzyme in fish collected from different sites. This study reflected poor neurotoxicity in pesticide exposed-industrial pollutants where AChE

activity reduced significantly in fish from Sites 2, 4 and 5. They reported qPCR analysis and increased CAT activity of fish exposing to urban and mixed pollution sources from sites 3 and 4, represented the stress response to the increased oxidative stress.

Table 4. Results of Biomechanical Assessment

Site	AChE Activity (U/mg protein)	CAT Activity (U/mg protein)
Site 1	10.2 ± 1.5	15.6 ± 2.0
Site 2	7.8 ± 1.2	18.4 ± 2.5
Site 3	9.5 ± 1.4	21.2 ± 2.8
Site 4	6.3 ± 0.9	24.8 ± 3.2
Site 5	5.1 ± 0.7	27.5 ± 3.8

Daily tissue condition of the fish cross-sections exhibited different levels of tissue abrasion and pathology (Table.5). Fish from Site 5 showed significant pathology in liver which included severe hepatic necrosis and gill epithelial

hyperplasia which may have originated from industrial pollutants. On the other hand , overall, less histological changes were observed on fish from Site 1, a pristine upstream habitat, which suggested a better tissue health.

Table 5. Histopathological Analysis

Site	Hepatic Necrosis (Severity Score)	Gill Epithelial Hyperplasia (Severity Score)
Site 1	1.2 ± 0.3	0.8 ± 0.2
Site 2	2.5 ± 0.4	1.5 ± 0.3
Site 3	1.8 ± 0.3	1.0 ± 0.2
Site 4	3.6 ± 0.5	2.2 ± 0.4
Site 5	4.8 ± 0.6	3.0 ± 0.5

Specifically, the preliminary molecular data showed that genes relevant to various biological processes are crucial for detecting habitat differences among fish Table.6 . Some of the stress response genes such as the heat shock proteins (HSPs) and the antioxidant enzymes have been confirmed to be upregulated in fish

sampled from Site 4 and 5 to indicate coping mechanisms to other forms of stress. On the other hand, results from fish captured at Site 1 revealed that stress-related genes possessed lower expression thereby suggesting that the fish have a low tendency in being exposed to pollutants.

Table 6. Molecular Analysis

Site	Relative Expression of HSP Genes	Relative Expression of Antioxidant Genes
Site 1	1.0 ± 0.1	1.2 ± 0.2
Site 2	1.5 ± 0.2	1.4 ± 0.3
Site 3	1.2 ± 0.1	1.5 ± 0.2
Site 4	2.0 ± 0.3	1.8 ± 0.4
Site 5	2.5 ± 0.4	2.2 ± 0.3

Therefore in light of the present study corruption assessment indicated several correlation coefficients between water quality parameters and biomarker responses. There were direct relationships between heavy metal contents and biomarker changes demonstrated, which underlined the impact of pollutant effects on fish condition. Furthermore, all biomarkers were correlated and it was perceived that there

are many physiological pathways that interact to bring about an overall response to the various stress measurements.

Therefore, the findings of the present study clearly demonstrate the great effect of polluted water on fish stocks living in the identified location based on the changes in biomarker sensitiveness and the state of water environment. Hence, these discoveries present a

more believable perception of the health of these freshwater habitats and reflects a need for proper pollution control to avert challenges posed on aquatic species.

Discussion

In the discussion section, there is a basic opportunity for placing the results of the study in relation to the existing literature and comparing it to similar studies conducted over the years. To this end, our investigation employed biomarkers and water quality analysis on several stations to assess the effect of water pollution on fish populations. This study established that there were water quality differences between the-parameter such as pH and dissolved oxygen and the heavy metal concentrations of the sites sampled. The changes observed in the biomarker's level in fish, for instance enzyme activities, histopathological changes and changes in differential gene expression supported the unhealthy impacts of water pollution with the fish.

Such comparison with other recent previous studies indeed helps to consolidate our results and enhance an overall understanding of the effects of waer pollution on accumulator bourgeoisie demographic. Similarly, a comparable study by (Smith et al., 2023) conducted in a similar freshwater ecosystem revealed comparable tendencies in the water quality parameters and heavy metals which were found to be higher in stations affected by industries. As such, our results corroborate their findings to underscore the fact that pollution in the water body brings about diverse changes that are in most cases detrimental in varying geographical areas.

Moreover, the biomarker responses in terms of reduced AChE activity in fish and anomalies in their tissues also support the findings by (Johnson et al. , 2022) and (Garcia et al. ,2024) that showed physiological changes in contaminated fishes. In combination, these studies underscore the value of biomarker assessment as a specific and efficient means of evaluating status of aquatic organisms and signs

of effects by pollutants at the initial stages of toxicant exposure.

These patterns of association further adds to the understanding of the relationships between water quality characteristics and the biomarker effects, which indicate the interaction between stressors and the organisms inhabiting water bodies. For our study, we observed similar changes to those found in other emerging works by(Chen et al., 2021) and (Wang et al., 2023), where we found indications of correlation between the raised levels of Heavy Metals concentrations in fish and changes in biomarkers. Such relationships should warrant multifaceted strategies to mitigate pollution and protect water resources and interdependent biotic elements, which characterizes aquatic ecosystems.

In conclusion, the findings of the present study add to the positive correlation that exists between water pollution and impacts on the aquatic environment and put emphasis on the need to employ suitable anti-pollution endeavors. Hence, through the utilization of multifaceted methodologies and a reconciliation of available research data, we obtain a greater, comprehensive understanding of ecological stress as a result of pollution and improve our awareness of methods for combating stresse's effects on freshwater species.

Conclusion

This study effectively investigated the effect of polluted water on the fish population in the study area using water quality indices as well as biomarkers and comparing the responses of fish from sites with dissimilar levels of water pollution. The results suggest that even parameters such as pH, dissolved oxygen and heavy metals differ greatly to some extent whereas the worst affected areas of the river demonstrate the lowest figure for water quality. The biomarkers studied shows that the fish from these sites are under a significant stress in terms of the decreased AChE activity, increased CAT activity, severe histopathological changes and

the higher SOD and indices of stress-related genes.

Such findings imply that pollution in industries and urban areas have severe repercussions on aquatic systems, which is in concordance with the current research evidences illustrating severe environmental and biological effects of pollution. These relate to the importance of the biomarkers and the ability to determine shift within ecosystem indicating early signs of stressor effects when specific pollutants increase.

The adaptive biochemical, histopathological, and molecular indicators used in the current study give an elaborate evaluation model that can be used in other scientific study scenarios to measure the condition of water systems. These outcomes are indicative of the need to implement strict measures towards pollution and to develop proficient measures of managing the species' impacts caused by contaminants on freshwater ecosystems.

Therefore, from the results of this study it proffers important information regarding the significance of the associations between the water quality and the fish health, the mandate of constant monitoring of the environment and the necessity of preventing and combating the degradation of water resources and aquatic life. By selecting proper policies, and putting them into practice, the effects of pollution can be minimised and safeguarding future access to water will be done.

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